

PREDISPOSING FACTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ACUTE LARYNGITIS

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Annotation. Acute laryngitis is an acute inflammation of the mucous membrane of the larynx. This disease can be both independent and a manifestation of some infectious diseases (ARVI, influenza, whooping cough, etc.) or general somatic diseases (rheumatism, gout, blood diseases). The cause of acute laryngitis is an infection, the pathogens of which constantly saprophytize in the larynx and are easily activated under the influence of a number of endogenous and exogenous factors. The occurrence of acute laryngitis is facilitated by general and local hypothermia, unfavorable working conditions (dusty rooms, hot dry air, increased background noise, etc.), as well as overstrain of the vocal apparatus. The disease can also be a result of trauma, chemical and thermal burns of the larynx.

Key words: Chronic laryngitis, larynx, acute inflammation of the mucous membrane.

Relevance. Predisposing factors for the development of acute laryngitis are chronic foci of inflammation: chronic pharyngitis, purulent sinusitis, chronic tonsillitis, nasal breathing disorders (curvature of the nasal septum, chronic hypertrophic rhinitis, etc.), as well as metabolic disorders, such as diabetes mellitus. Histological examination of the laryngeal mucosa in acute laryngitis determines its damage. The ciliated epithelium loses cilia or is rejected, deeper layers of cells are preserved (they serve as a matrix for epithelial regeneration). With a pronounced inflammatory process, metaplasia of the atrial fibrillation of the cylindrical epithelium into a flat one may occur. The infiltration of the mucous membrane is expressed unevenly, the blood vessels are convoluted, dilated, and overflowing with blood. In some cases, their subepithelial ruptures are detected (more often in the area of the vocal folds). It is known that the microflora colonizing the non-sterile parts of the respiratory tract, including in the larynx, is represented by saprophytic microorganisms that almost never cause diseases in humans, and conditionally pathogenic bacteria capable of causing purulent inflammation under unfavorable conditions for the macroorganism. Microgroups that are considered to be among the most common pathogens include *S. pneumoniae* and *H. influenzae*. In addition, *Moraxella catarrhalis*, various types of creptococci and statilococci, primarily representatives of the genus *Neisseria*, corynebacteria, etc., are most often found. The role of atypical pathogens of infections of the ENT organs (chlamydia, mycoplasma, etc.), which, being intracellular parasites, change the course of the underlying disease, causing inflammation of other body tissues, is becoming increasingly relevant.

Conclusions: Thus, at the beginning of the disease, patients complain of a feeling of dryness, scratching, and sore throat. The voice becomes rough, hoarseness gradually develops, sometimes up to aphonia. Voice changes are caused by inflammatory edema of the mucous membrane of the vocal folds and larynx, increased sputum formation. On the 2nd–3rd day of the disease, a dry cough may appear. It is accompanied by a scanty separation of viscous mucous sputum, the amount of which may increase in the future, and the character may change up to purulent, especially when tracheitis is attached.

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